

**PRINCIPLES OF AYURVEDA TOWARDS THE PREVENTATION OF LIFESTYLE
DISORDERS: A SAMHITA BASED REVIEW****Dr. Rameshwar Aglave*¹, Dr. Lata Srivastava², Dr. Rama Nand³**

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18797272>

How to cite this Article: Dr. Rameshwar Aglave*¹, Dr. Lata Srivastava², Dr. Rama Nand³ (2026). Principles Of Ayurveda Towards The Prevention Of Lifestyle Disorders: A Samhita Based Review. World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research, 12(3), 01–05.

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Article Received on 26/01/2026

Article Revised on 16/02/2026

Article Published on 01/03/2026

ABSTRACT

Lifestyle diseases can be defined as the diseases linked to the manner in which a person lives their life. These are caused by unhealthy lifestyle such as poor diet, bad eating habits, lack of physical activity, insomnia, psychological stress, smoking and intake of excessive alcohol. Lifestyle disorders globally killing 38millions of people every year whereas In India, one out of four is at risk of dying from lifestyle disorder. The treatment for lifestyle disorder management in Ayurveda is given as per individual bodily constitutions depending on their medical history, current conditions and previous treatment so that it best suits the patients. All regimens of Ayurveda aim not only to counter the specific symptoms of the body but also to achieve proper balance. Ayurvedic lifestyle promotes physical, mental as well as social health and ultimately leads to symptomatic improvement. Ayurveda offers various methods to manage life-style disorders by following Aahar, Dinacharya, Ritucharya, Panchakarma therapy, Rasayana therapy. Ayurveda in order to apply measures in preventing the upcoming epidomic of lifestyle disorders which are preventable with changes in diet, lifestyle and environment.

KEYWORDS: Lifestyle diseases, Aahar, Dinacharya, Rasayana, Sadvritta.**INTRODUCTION**

Lifestyle diseases are the ailments that are primarily linked with one's lifestyle. The distraction of one's from enough physical or mental activity and push them towards sedentary lifestyle either due to their habits or their busy schedule or routines. Main causes of lifestyle disorder if not managed or prevented, these can lead to life threatening consequences with time.

Hypertension, diabetes, PCOS, cancer, arthritis, obesity, insomnia, depression are the diseases which can be taken under lifestyle disorders. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), lifestyle disorder are a subgroup of non-communicable diseases (NCDs) which kill around 41 million people each year, that is around 71% of all deaths globally. NCDs are usually

chronic in nature and cannot be communicated from one person to another.

To sustain a healthy and joyful life (Hitaayu & Sukhaayu), Ayurvedahas a number of different principles and regimens including Ahara And Vihar(dietary habits and daily routine), Dinacharya(daily regimen), Ratricharya(night regimen), Ritucharya(seasonal regimen), Panchkarma(five detoxification and bio-purification therapies), Rasayana(rejuvenation), Sadvritta paalan(ideal habits) and Aachara Rasayana(code of conduct). Hence, lifestyle disorders can be well managed through Ayurvedaby adopting its different principles and regimens.^[1]

AIM

Ayurvedic principles to prevent lifestyle disorders.

OBJECTIVES

To evaluate the principles of ayurveda for healthy life.
To evaluate ayurvedic prevention of lifestyle disorders.

MATERIALS AND METHODS**Materials**

Various ayurvedic classic texts including Charakasamhita, Sushrut samhita, Ashtanghridaya were consulted as source material. Apart from this, various research journals, websites have been thoroughly searched.

Methods

- Ahara
- Dincharya
- Rutucharya
- Rasayan
- Vajikarana
- Achara rasayan
- Sadvrita

Top lifestyle diseases

WHO states the top 10 lifestyles diseases in the world affecting health are as follows:

1. Alzheimers disease
2. Arteriosclerosis
3. Cancer
4. Chronic liver disease/cirrhosis
5. Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD)
6. Diabetes
7. Heart disease
8. Nephritis
9. Stroke
10. Obesity^[2]

How lifestyle disorders formed

In ancient times, people were following the ideal Lifestyle. Therefore, people were not much get affected by various types of diseases. Afterward, it has been turned into a sedentary lifestyle. In the modern era of civilization, due to the growing use of technologies and increasing competition, changing lifestyles has become a leading cause of manifestation of many diseases like Diabetes mellitus, Obesity, etc. Lifestyle disorders are the results of an unbalanced diet. One could get trapped in a lifestyle disorder if their eating habits are linked to skipping meals, overeating, and high intake of sugar and oily foods. A person who follows an unhealthy diet takes nutrition in all its forms. They are also easily affected by lifestyle related health issues such as diabetes, stroke and heart diseases.

Causes

Diet: Poor nutrition, eating too much processed food, and consuming a diet high in saturated fats, sugars, and salt.

Physical activity: Lack of regular physical activity.

Sleep: Not getting enough sleep.

Tobacco use: Smoking tobacco and exposure to second-hand smoke

Alcohol use: Excessive alcohol use

Stress: Chronic stress

Drugs: Using drugs

Exposure to pollutants: Exposure to pollutants at work or home

Habits that damage the body: Using earphones or poor seating.^[3]

AYURVEDIC PRINCIPLES FOR PREVENTATION OF LIFE STYLE DISORDERS**1. AHARA (PROPER DIETARY MANAGEMENT)**

Ahara is one of the important pillars of Ayurveda. It means that it is one of the basic principles upon which health, happiness, and harmony rest. Nowadays there is an increased prevalence of lifestyle disorders, in which faulty dietary habits play an important role. Unhealthy food and faulty dietary habits give origin to various life-threatening lifestyle disorders. For good health, a person should always eat a balanced diet and avoid incompatible dietary regimens. It is said in ancient Indian literature that if dietetics is followed, medicine is not needed and if dietetics is not observed, even medicines do not get proper results. The rules and methods of diet intake are mentioned in Charaksamhita as ashtaah aravidhi visheshayatana. It is a very important aspect regarding dietetics that when to take food. Ayurveda also recommended warm water is good for digestive health. Ayurveda also described eighteen types of dietary incompatibilities (VirruddhaAhara) which should be avoided to maintain health and longevity.

ashta vidha aahar visheshayatana

1. Prakriti: Denotes the natural quality of the food like Guru, Laghu etc. which help in choosing the foods according to our digestion capacity.

2. Karan: Food needs to be processed and transformed into a consumable form. Methods include - Toya Sannikarsha, Agni Sannikarsha, Shoucha, Manthana, Desha, Kala, Vasana, Bhavana, Kala Prakarsha, Bhajana.

3. Samyoga: Honey and ghee when mixed in equal proportions lethal and are dangerous for health.

4. Rashi: Quantity of intake of food is very important for conducive health. Two types of Rashi - 1) Sarvagraha Rashi, 2) Parigraha Rashi

5. Desha: Place where the food items are grown or cultivated. Three types of Desha-

1) Jangala-Vata predominant,

2) Anupa-Kapha predominant,

3) Sadharana - moderate zones

6. Kala: Some people follow and are very particular and punctual with respect to time of consumption of food. Two types of Kala - Nityaga Kala & Avasthika Kala.

Rules of ahar Intake**Ushnamasniyata**

We should consume Ushna Aahar which is in delicious taste. Ushna Aahar activate Jathragni and factor

responsible for digestion. It helps in Anuloma of Vata and detachment of Kapha.

Snighamasthiyata

Provoke the digestive power. It helps in the alleviation of Vata and increase Bala, Varna, Sharir and power of sense organ.

Matravasthiyata

“*Aahar Matra Tu Agni Bala Apekshini*”. One should eat in proper quantity. Food taken in proper quantity without disturbing Vata, Pitta and Kapha only promotes life-span, easily passes down to anus, does not disturb the (digestive) fire, gets digested with comfort; hence one should eat in proper quantity.

Jirneasthiyata

One should eat when the previous meal is digested because if one eats during indigestion, the eaten food mixing the product of the earlier meal with that of the later one vitiates all the Dosas quickly, on the contrary, when one eats after the previous meal is digested well, the Dosas are situated in their own locations, Agni is stimulated, appetite is arisen, entrances of the channels are open, eructation is pure, heart is normal, flatus passes down and urges of flatus, urine and faeces are attended to, the eaten food promotes only the life-span without afflicting any Dhatu. Hence one should eat after the previous meal is digested.

Viravirudhamasthiyata

One should take food having no contradictory potencies. Diseases caused by Viruddha Ahara are as Adhmana, Aamavisha, Grahani, Amlapitta etc. which lead to Lifestyle disorders.

Istedeshe, Istasarpokaranamasthiyata

One should take food in favorable place and with favorable accessories that it does not get afflicted with such of the factors as would result in emotional strain.

Naativilambitam

One should not take food too slow because it does not give satisfaction to individual. Food would become cold and there will be irregularity of digestion.

Naatidrutam

One should not take food too fast because it may enter into wrong passage.

Ajalpana, Ahasana, Tanmananahunjita

By taking food while talking or laughing or with mind elsewhere, is inflicted with the defects as by eating too fast.

Atmanamabhisamiksya

One should eat after due consideration to his self. This is suitable or unsuitable for me if known in this way then only it becomes suited to his self.^[4]

2. DINCHARYA

Dinacharya are ideal daily life routine instructions which if followed as life style shall prevent life style related problems. This not only helps in provision of physical health but also attain mental and social health. Ayurveda suggests to begin daily habits with awareness, early rising, avoid suppression of natural urges and eliminate waste as per urge, keep the teeth & skin cleaned, regular use of massage, regular daily bathing, consume suitable and wholesome diet according to the appetite and metabolic needs.^[5]

Ayurveda is the science which emphasized the preventive aspect. Dinacharya is one of the principles mentioned in Ayurveda in the context of prevention. The activities or regimen which needs to be followed daily, by every individual is called Dinacharya. It is advisable to wake up during Brahma Muhurta (preferably between 4.00 a.m. to 5.30 a.m.). One should attend nature's calls. The soft brushes made out of twigs of Khadira, Karanja, Apamarga, etc. should be used for brushing the teeth. It is necessary to massage (Abhyanga) whole body with medicated oil every day. Oil massage ensures softness and unctuousness of skin, free movement of joints and muscles. The application of collyrium (Anjana) in the eyes should be done regularly. Regular exercise (vyayama) is essential for perfect health. It builds up stamina and resistance against diseases, clears the channels of the body (Srotas), and increases the blood circulation. Whole-body massage with dry powders of yawa, kulath (Udvartan) every day. It is necessary to do Nasya daily. Nasyadravyas triggers the nerve endings and sends the message to the CNS and initiates the normal physiological functions of the body. Bathing (Snana) improves strength, appetite, enthusiasm, a span of life, and removes sweat and other impurities from the body.^[6]

3. RITUCHARYA

These are primarily set of instructions which if ideally followed as per season shall help individual to physically and biologically to a particular season as well as make him free of seasonal ailments. These include dietic instructions, clothing instructions as well as some behavioural practices, which besides other guidelines include shodhana (bio-purification) as per seasonal needs.^[7]

Ritucharya represents a very important aspect of a preventive measure for various illnesses including lifestyle disorders as mentioned in Ayurvedic text Whole year is divided into six seasons (Shishira, Vasant, Greeshma, Varsha, Sharad, Hemant). A specific regimen has been mentioned in these seasons which includes Vamana in Vasant Ritu; Virechanain Sharad Ritu; Basti in Varsha Ritu. In the spring season, bitter, hot and astringent diet is advised while salty, sour food should be avoided. In the summer season due to the hot climate, aggravation of pitta occurs. Hence, pitta pacifying sweets, unctuous and liquid diet is advised. The

excessive hot, spicy, sour, salty diet should be avoided. In rainy season aggravation of vata occurs, hence vatashamaka sweet, sour foods are preferred. In pre-winter and winter season vatadosha aggravates due to cold dry atmosphere, hence vataghna diet is recommended.^[8]

People ignore the food to eat in specific seasons, dressing, and other regimens to be followed in a particular season or stressful life leads to derangement of homeostasis and causes various lifestyle disorders. It is postulated that if an individual follows the prescribed ritucharya, he may adopt and overcome the stresses of seasonal variations and may not suffer from ill-health.

4. PANCHAKARMA (FIVE DETOXIFICATION AND BIOPURIFICATION THERAPIES)

Panchakarma is one of the most emerging parts of Ayurveda as it plays a very important role in the effective management of lifestyle disorders which are on increase at a high rate. Panchakarma is a method of biopurification, as they possess properties being real pathogenesis breaker, long-standing effects, and fewer chances of recurrences of diseases. Panchakarma purifies and detoxifies the body by expelling metabolic toxins and in maintaining normal functioning of the body, improving metabolism and body coordinations.

The five technologies of Panchakarma include Vaman (therapeutic emesis), Virechan (therapeutic purgation), Asthapan Basti (therapeutic decoction enema), Anuwasana Basti (therapeutic oil enema) and Nasya Karma (nasal medication). All the Panchakarma regimens are followed to achieve the homeostasis and not just counter the specific symptom. Panchakarma is claimed for its preventive, promotive, prophylactic and rejuvenative properties. Panchakarma places equal focus on preventive and curative measures. Both physical and emotional wellness are addressed by Shirodhara and Nasya. Additional Panchakarma treatments also improve mental health, lower stress, and avoid lifestyle disorders.

5. RASAYANA (REJUVENATION THERAPY)

Rasayanas can be used as nutritional supplements as well as medicine depending upon its various types. Most Rasayanas produce their nourishing and rejuvenating effect by promoting the Agni bala, acting as direct nutrients and by way of srotoprasadana resulting in an improved nutritional status which further leads to an improved quality of Dhatus or body tissues.^[9]

Rasayanas are a generic class of restorative and rejuvenating supplements, many Rasayanas could be tissue and organ-specific such as *Medhya Rasayana* for the brain, *Hridya Rasayana* for the heart. *Twachya Rasayana* for the skin and so on¹⁸. The application of organ-specific Rasayana herbs also provides enough scope not only for the prevention of diseases but also for the promotion of health and cure of diseases too.^[10]

Various studies on Rasayana drugs suggest their following action

- Immunomodulator
- Adaptogenic Antioxidant
- Nootropic
- Antistress Anticancer
- Psychoneuro stability.

Rasayana in various diseases

Netra roga – Triphala, Shatavari, Yashtimadhu

Prameha – Haridra, Shilajatu, Amalaki

Amavata – Bhallataka, Lasuna, Pippali

Nervous Disorders – Bala, Nagabala, Ashwagandha

Skin diseases – Tugaraka, Guduchi, Bhringaraja

Urinary tract – Gokshura, Punarnava, Shilajit

GI tract – Amalaki, Haritaki, Guduchi, Vidanga,

Shatavari **Vatavyadhi** – Shilajit, Guggulu, Chyavanaprasha

Pandu – Yograj rasayana, Loha, Shilajit

Mental disorders – Brahmi, Jyotismati, Mandukaparni.^[11]

6. SADVRITTA & ACHARA RASAYANA

Ayurveda offers some code of good conducts under the heading of Sadvritta and Achara Rasayana which helps in maintaining a healthy body and a peaceful mind. Sadvritta means physical and mental decorum which should be followed by everyone daily.

In Charaka Samhita Sutrasthana detailed description of Sadvritta has been stated. The following code of conduct of sadvritta should be followed.

1. Speak the truth and use pleasant words in conversation
2. Do not lose your temper under any circumstances
3. Do not get addicted to sensory pleasures.
4. Abstain from telling lies, anger, extreme grief, jealousy and greed
5. Observe self-control
6. As far as possible, do not expose yourself to hardships.
7. Do not harm anyone
8. Avoid suppression of natural urges
9. Be patient. Be straight forward and kind
10. Avoid overeating, overdrinking, too much sexual activity, too much or too little sleep .
11. Control your sense organs
12. Make a habit of doing all that is good and avoiding all that is bad.^[12]

Acharya Sushruta considers a man healthy only when he is in the state of biological balance and enjoyssensorial, mental, and spiritual wellbeing Such a state of health can be achieved only by observing the rules of good conduct i.e sadvritta.

CONCLUSION

Lifestyle disease is internationally known as Non-Communicable diseases (NCDs) these are mainly result from physical inactivity and junk food etc.

Nowadays the lifestyle disorders are affecting today's society, as one of the quotations says that Prevention is better than cure. We can prevent these lifestyle disorders by maintaining our lifestyle through Ayurveda. Ayurveda offers an effective and safe solution in the form of proper dietary management, lifestyle advises panchakarma (bio purification procedures), and rejuvenation therapy to prevent lifestyle disorders.

Aachara Rasayana and Sadvritta have gradual impacts of psychological and emotional conduct. By adhering to the Dinacharya, Ritucharya, Panchakarma and Rasayana treatment, we can prevent lifestyle problems and much more help full to attained happy, healthy and prosperous life. So be happy, stay healthy and adopt Ayurveda in your life today.

Charaka sutrasthan, Indriyopakramaniya adhyaya, 2020; 5.

REFERENCES

1. Singh R.H. The Basic Tenets of Ayurvedic Dietetics and Nutrition. In: S. Rastogi, editors. Ayurvedic science of Food and Nutrition, New York: Springer, 2014; 1: 15-23.
2. World health organization fact sheets noncommunicable diseases- <https://www.who.int/newsroom/factsheets/detail/noncommunicable-diseases>.
3. Thakkar Jayesh, Chaudhar's, Sarka Prasanta K. Ritucharya: Answer to lifestyle disorders. AYU, 2011; 32 (4): 466471.
4. Sastri Kasinath, Chaturvedi Gorkhnath, Charakasamhita, Chaukhambha Bharati Academy, Charaka Vimanasthan, Rasavimana, 2020; 1.
5. Sastri Kasinath, Chaturvedi Gorkhnath, Charakasamhita, Chaukhambha Bharati Academy Charaka sutrasthan, Matrasheetiya adhyaya, 2020; 5.
6. Tripathy Bramhananda, Ashtanga hridaya, Chaukhamba subharati prakashan, sutrasthana, Dinacharya, 2014; 2.
7. Tripathy Bramhananda, Ashtanga hridaya, Chaukhamba subharati prakashan, sutrasthana, Ritucharya adhyaya, 2014; 3.
8. Sastri Kasinath, Chaturvedi Gorkhnath, Charakasamhita, Chaukhambha Bharati Academy Charaka sutrasthan, Tasyashitiya adhyaya, 2020; 6.
9. Sastri Kasinath, Chaturvedi Gorkhnath, Charakasamhita, Chaukhambha Bharati Academy, Charaka chikitsasthan, Rasayana adhyaya (Abhayamalakiya Rasayana Pada, Pranakamiyam Rasayana Pada, Karaprachitiam Rasayana Pada, Ayurvedasamutthaniyam Rasayana Pada), 2020; 1.
10. Tripathy Bramhananda Ashtang hridaya, Chaukhamba subharati Prakashan, uttaratantra Rasayanavidhi Adhyaya, 2014; 39.
11. Bhavamishra Bhavaprakasha (original text along with commentary and translation) Comm. By Dr. Bulususitaram, chaukhamba Orientalia, Varanasi, 2012; 1, 6(2): 8-131.
12. Sastri Kasinath, Chaturvedi Gorkhnath, Charakasamhita, Chaukhambha Bharati Academy